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Research Article

**FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF MOUTH
DISSOLVING DRUG DELIVERY OF WAFER FOR THE
TREATMENT OF ALLERGIC DISORDER**¹Ashuthosh Badola, ²Neha¹Assistant Professor School Of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Shri Guru Ram Rai University.,²Department of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Shri Guru Ram Rai University, Patel Nagar Dehradun,
Uttarakhand, India.**Article Received:** November 2020 **Accepted:** December 2020 **Published:** January 2021**Abstract:**

The lyophilized wafer developed throughout this review is an effective and versatile drug delivery system for or mucosal application. This has been established from the extensive physicochemical and physic mechanical profiling conducted. Through a screening and selection of polymers, HPC had the lowest gelatin characteristics and was therefore suitable for the development of the wafer system. Suitable excipients and polymer combinations were established which allowed for the development of rapidly disintegrating and prolonged release wafer systems. The wafer system containing HPC, lactose, mannitol and glycine had the ability to disintegrate within 30 seconds. The modified wafer system, consisting of pectin cross linked with zinc ions serving as the drug reservoir, and mucoadhesive polymer combination of pectin caramelizes and gelatin, provided effective release of model drug diphenhydramine hydrochloride over approximately six hours. The modification of this technology to provide a prolonged release mucoadhesive system seems promising. It is envisaged that this system will be applicable to many drugs requiring the extended release of bioactive material. Therefore, the lyophilized wafer matrices developed in this study are highly effective in the rapid delivery of drugs, using the oral route as a site of administration.

Keywords: Glioblastoma, glycosphingolipids, acylceramides, matrices and lyophilized.**Corresponding author:****Ashuthosh Badola,**Assistant Professor School Of Pharmaceutical Sciences,
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QR code

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INTRODUCTION:

Formulation consideration among the novel drug delivery system buccal drug delivery is the main and extensive acceptable drug delivery between the other delivery system. The innovation designs may involve modifying formulation composition and manufacturing technologies to achieve new product endpoint. Among the fast-dissolving drug delivery system, oral flash release wafer drug delivery system is an alternative to tablet capsules and syrups for pediatric and geriatric patient who experience in difficulties of swallowing traditional oral solid Dosage form. This technology has been used for local action rapid release of product and direct Systemic circulation in the oral cavity to release drug in rapid fashion. The pharmaceutical wafers hold potential advantages like rapid disintegration no swallowing or chewing, no administration of water, accurate dosing compared to liquid products great safety and efficacy along with the patient compliance Buccal dosage forms include mucoadhesive tablets films patches ointment hydro gels, each of which has limitations. Wafers products are available to patients for immediate release of several API. Wafers an innovative oral dosage forms new oral thin films so called wafers thus creating new possibilities for action profiles and patient compliance. Wafers are paper thin polymer film used as carriers for pharmaceutical agents. The 2008FDA guidance recommends a disintegration time of 30seconds or less based on Us Pharmacopoeia disintegration test method and maximum tablet weight of 500mg. ODTs are Preferred by multiple patients groups with swallowing difficulties ,including geriatrics ,dysphasic ,and extension for first to market product and marketing differentiation for over the counter Products .And also this delivery protect drug form first pass metabolism and improve the Dissolution .Oral thin wafer drug delivery system are solid dosage forms which dissolve in a Short period of time when placed in the mouth without drinking water These are also referred as fast dissolving oral wafers, buccal films.

The rational for development and use of novel drug delivery system may include one or more the following arguments:

1. Decrease the toxicity and occurrence of adverse drug and metabolism in the blood at the target sites.
2. Attractive dosage form with new active ingredients.
3. Improve drug utilization by applying a smaller drug dose in a controlled–release form to Produce the same clinical effect as a larger dose in a conventional dosage form.
4. Provide greater patient convenience and better patient compliance by significantly prolonging interval between administrations.
5. Improvement of established products.
6. Provide a uniform blood concentration and or provide a more predictable drug delivery.
7. Optimization of bioavailability
8. Increase patient compliance.
9. Innovative technology for product.
10. Increase of product appeal through innovative formula.
11. Exclusivity and cutting-edge technology position in the market through a step forward.
12. Access to new indications by means of a new absorption profile even for exists in active ingredients.

Anatomic and Physiologic Features of the Oral Cavity:

The surface area of the oral mucosa is about 100 cm². Three different types of Oral mucosa are recognized: the mucosa, the lining mucosa, and the specialized Mucosa. The masticator mucosa, representing 25% of the total oral mucosa, is 100–200µm thick and covers the gingival and the hard palate. It is tightly attached to underlying structures and subjected to abrasion and shear stress during mastication. The lining mucosa (60% of the total oral mucosa) is 500–800µm thick and covers the lips, cheeks, soft palate, and lower surface of the tongue and the floor of the oral cavity.

The specialized mucosa (15% of the total oral mucosa) is present on the dorsum of the tongue and is involved in taste.

Mucosal region of mouth [10]

Fig 4: Composition of layers of mucosal epithelium

Fig 5: Absorption through oral mucosal

Advantages of wafers technology:

- No first pass effect
- High dissolution due to a large surface area.
- More patient compliance
- Reduced impact on the gastrointestinal tract
- Low dose can only be incorporated.
- Discrete and easy application
- Better durable than oral-dispersible tablets
- No risk of choking
- Improved bio-availability, translates to lower dose

Types of wafers:

- Flash dissolved wafers.
- Melt away wafers.
- Sustained release wafers.
- Flash dispersed wafers.

EXPERIMENTAL:

Materials and methods:

Materials:

LOR, hydroxyl propels cellulose (HPC) (Klucel) and saccharine sodium was purchased Fr Yarrow Chemical Products, Mumbai, India; sodium carboxyl methyl cellulose (Sod. CMC), lactose monohydrate, polyethylene glycol 400 were obtained from Merck Specialities Pvt. Ltd., India; sorbitol (liquid 70 %) was procured from CDH, India; glycerol was purchased from Lobar chime, Mumbai, India. All the other chemicals and solvents used were of AR grade and used without further purification.

Preparation of LOR bio- adhesive pharmaceutical wafers:

Method-1

Numerous literatures had revealed the use of solvent casting method to prepare bio adhesive thin films or wafers (Cilurzo et al. 2008; El-Setouhy and El-Malak 2010). Here we have utilized this procedure for development of the wafers. 2 %w/v of HPC was considered as films forming polymer and mixed with varied amount of Sodium CMC as per the experimental design (Table 2), where HPC concentration was kept constant in all formulations and was dispersed in required volume of distilled water and kept overnight for soaking.

A constant proportion of propylene glycol, glycerin and sorbitol were used as plasticizers.

Required amount of LOR dissolved in aliquot of ethanol was dispersed in the polymer dispersion with continuous stirring. Lactose monohydrate was added in the dispersion with continuous stirring followed by addition of saccharine sodium (sweetener) and peppermint (favors). The stirring process of the total polymeric dispersion was continued for 6 h.

The dispersion was kept in degasser for 180 s to remove any dissolved gas. 25 ml of the solution was casted in polypropylene Petri plates (Poly lab Industries Pvt. Ltd., India) and kept overnight to remove the entrapped air bubbles. The content of the plates were dried at 45 °C. Wafers of 2.2 diameters were cut within-house fabricated hollow punch and kept in desiccator, maintained at a relative humidity of 60 ± 5 % until further analysis.

TABLE 1: Composition of the casting solution as per experimental design to prepare wafer formulation FNA.

Ingredients	FNC Code
Na Alginate	1%w/v
HPMC	1%w/v
PG	2%w/v
Ethanol	15%w/v
Lactose monohydrate	-----
Loratadine	0.134w/v
Glycerin	1.5%w/v
Sorbitol	0.5%w/v
Water/Peppermint	q.s

Evaluation of mucoadhesive pharmaceutical Wafers

Appearance

The tablets were visually observed for capping

Weight Variation

Method

Twenty tablets were randomly selected from each batch and individually weighed. The average weight and standard deviation of 20 tablets was calculated. The batch passes the test for weight variation test if not more than two of the individual tablet weight deviates from the average weight.

Table: 2. Specifications of % weight variation allowed in tablets as per Indian Pharmacopoeia

Average Weight of Tablet	% Deviation Allowed
80mg	10
More than 80 mg but less than 250mg	7.5
250mg or more	5

Surface pH measurement:

The wafers were left to swell for 10 min on the surface of an agar plate (2 % m/v in isotonic phosphate buffer pH 6.75). The surface pH was measured by means of a pH paper placed on the surface of the swollen wafer. The mean of three readings was recorded (Nafee et al. 2003a, b).

Surface morphology analysis:

Dried placebo and drug-loaded wafers were examined under a SEM (JEOL-JSM-6360, JEOL Datum Ltd., Tokyo, Japan). SEM photographs of samples were taken at 12 kV intensity at magnifications of 250–2,000.

Drug polymer Interaction analysis:

ATR–FTIR spectroscopy of prepared wafers ATR–FTIR spectra of blank wafer, LOR and LOR loaded wafer were recorded on a Burke—ALPHA FTIR spectrophotometer with software Opurunity

Hardness (Lehman L, 1991; Banker G.S., 1996)

Hardness or tablet crushing strength (For) the force required to break a tablet in a diametric compression was measured using Monsanto Hardness Tester. For each formulation, the hardness of 6 tablets was determined using the Monsanto hardness tester. The tablet was held along its oblong axis in between the two jaws of the tester. At this point, reading should be zero kg/cm². Then constant force was applied by rotating the knob until the tablet fractured. The value at this point was noted in kg/cm².

Friability:

Rapidly disintegrating systems prepared by the process of Lyophilization are known for having the characteristic disadvantage of poor physical resistance (Dobetti, 2001). Problems anticipated as a result of this include: breakage of tablet edges during handling and the inability of the tablet to be ejected and removed from a conventional blister alveolus. These features need to be taken into consideration when determining the packaging of the product. Friability was measured using a Roche Friabilator (Hoffman la Roche, Basel, Switzerland). The wafers (N=3) were

accurately weighed before being placed into the Friabilator. A rotation time of 4 minutes at 25 rpm was used. Tablets were removed and loose particles brushed off the surface. Wafers were re-weighed and the percentage weight loss was calculated.

$\% F = (\text{Initial wt.} - \text{Final wt.} / \text{Initial wt.}) \times 100.$

Weight Uniformity:

Weight uniformity was used to assess the reproducibility of wafer production process.

Polymer mean(g)	±SD
HPC 0.126	±0.0017
HPMC 0.122	±0.0002
Pectin 0.134	±0.0055
PVA 0.118	±0.0011
PEO 0.199	±0.0045
Sodium alginate	±0.0007

In vitro analysis of buccoadhesion:

A TAXT2i Texture Analyzer was used for in vitro bio adhesion analysis of the pharmaceutical wafers taking bovine buccal mucosa as a model membrane. The Buccal mucosal tissue was obtained from local slaughter house, cleaned, washed and stored at -20 C. Preserved, cleaned and thawed buccal mucosa was hydrated with simulated saliva solution and allowed to reach norm Weight Uniformity: Weight uniformity was used to assess the reproducibility of wafer production process. Individual wafers were weighed, and standard deviations calculated. All experimentation was conducted in triplicate. The reproducibility of the production process was demonstrated by the low standard deviations (SD) calculated from the mass for each of the various Polymer systems. Shows the results obtained from the various polymer wafer systems. Mean weight of wafers manufactured (N=3) at temperature before conducting the experiment.

The Buccal mucosa was tied to the lower probe of the assembly. The wafer was attached to the upper probe of the assembly using double-sided adhesive. The upper probe was allowed to fall on the lower probe with test speed 0.5 mm/s and post test speed 1 mm/s. The wafer was allowed to adhere to the bovine buccal mucosa membrane with applied force 150 g, return distance 10 mm. The experiment was carried out at room temperature (Ahmad et al. 2008; Hassan et al. 2010).

Individual wafers were weighed, and standard deviations calculated. All experimentation was conducted in triplicate. The reproducibility of the production process was demonstrated by the low standard deviations (SD) calculated from the mass for each of the various polymer systems. Shows the results obtained from the various polymer wafer systems. Mean weight of wafers manufactured (N=3)

Dissolution experiment:

The in vitro drug release of the wafers has been carried out by performing the dissolution experiment in a paddle type dissolution apparatus (Excel enterprises, Kolkata, India) equipped with six baskets. In order to mimic the in vivo adhesion and to prevent the wafers from floating, each wafer was fixed to a rectangular glass slab and placed at the bottom of the dissolution vessel prior to starting the dissolution test. The dissolution medium comprised of 250 ml of simulated salivary fluid pH 6.75. The rotation speed was kept at 50 rpm at 37 ± 0.5 C. At regular intervals of time (30 s), sample aliquots were withdrawn, filtered through a 0.45 μ m membrane filter and analyzed by UV spectrophotometer at a λ_{max} value of 248 nm. The withdrawn amount of dissolution medium was calculated. Cumulative percentage of drug released in the respective dissolution medium was plotted as a function of time. Each formulation was tested and analyzed in triplicate.

Disintegration Study:

The wafer size required for dose delivery (3.80cm²) was placed on a glass Petri dish containing 10mL of distilled water. The time required for the wafer to break was noted as in vitro disintegration time. All experimentation was done in triplicate. The disintegration process was visualized with optical scanning electronic microscope (RLMSCOPE, model number SM1500, Bikash Scientific Instruments, WB, India). The photographs were given in Figure 1.

Table3: Response parameter for Loratadine-loaded mucoadhesive pharmaceutical wafers prepared as per 32 factorial designs.

Formulation code Sod. Alginate	Formulation composition Lactose monohydrate	Bio adhesive time (Y1)(gm)	D.T (Y2)(min)	%swelling (Y3)	Tmax(Y4)(sec)
FNA 1 (0, -1)	1.00	0.00	28.26	1.09	90
FNA 2 (0, 0)	1.00	0.50	35.9	1.22	90
FNA 3 (0, +1)	1.00	1.00	25.9	1.247	240
FNA 4 (+1,-1)	1.50	0.00	40	1.367	90
FNA 5 (+1, 0)	1.50	0.50	65	1.683	120
FNA 6 (+1, +1)	1.50	1.00	81.2	2.067	210
FNA 7 (-1, -1)	0.50	0.00	61.3	0.316	30
FNA 8 (-1, 0)	0.50	0.50	38.9	0.453	90
FNA 9 (-1, +1)	0.50	1.00	34.4	0.476	180

Figure 1 Scanning electronic microscopic photographs (250 xs) of the wafer disintegration process at different time intervals.

in-vitro Dissolution studies:

The in vitro drug release of the wafers has been carried out by performing the dissolution experiment in a paddle type dissolution apparatus (Excel enterprises, Kolkata, India) equipped with six baskets. In order to mimic the in vivo adhesion and to prevent the wafers from floating, each wafer was fixed to a rectangular glass slab and placed at the bottom of the dissolution vessel prior to starting the dissolution test. The dissolution medium comprised of 250 ml of simulated salivary fluid (Koland et al. 2011) pH 6.75. The rotation speed was kept at 50

rpm at 37 ± 0.5 °C. At regular intervals of time (30 s) (Garsuch and Breikreutz 2009), sample aliquots were withdrawn, filtered through a 0.45 μ m membrane filter and analyzed by UV spectrophotometer (Thermo Scientific UV1) at a fixed λ_{max} value of 248 nm. The withdrawn amount of dissolution medium was calculated. Cumulative percentage of drug released in the respective dissolution medium was plotted as a function of time. Each formulation was tested and analyzed in triplicate (El-Setouhy and El-Malak 2010; El-Meshad and El-Hagrasy 2011).

Fig.-1 wafer after the dissolution test: (a) HPMC wafer (b) CMC wafer was fully dissolved.

Fig 2: Wafer after the dissolution test (a) HPMC wafer (b) CMC wafer was fully dissolved

In Vitro Release Study:

The in vitro drug release of the wafers was determined using a paddle type dissolution apparatus (Excel Enterprises, Kolkata, India). In order to mimic the in vivo adhesion and to prevent the wafers from floating, each wafer was fixed to a rectangular glassy band placed at the bottom of the dissolution vessel prior to starting the dissolution test. The dissolution medium was 250mL of simulated salivary fluid. The rotation speed was 50rpm at $37^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 0.5^{\circ}\text{C}$. The drug release was analyzed spectrophotometrically at 248nm. Every 30s, 5mL samples were manually drawn, filtered through a $0.45\text{-}\mu\text{m}$ membrane filter, and analyzed by UV-VIS spectroscopy (Thermo Scientific UV1). The withdrawn amount of dissolution medium was calculated. The measurement was made in triplicate with the standard deviation as a measure of variation.

Optimization Data Analysis:

Various RSM computations for the current optimization study were performed employing Design-Experts of t ware (Trialversion 8.0.7.1, Stat Ease Inc., Minneapolis, MN, USA). Statistical second-order model including interaction and polynomial terms was generated for all the response variables.

The general form of the model is represented as in the following:

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 A + \beta_2 B + \beta_3 AB + \beta_4 A^2 + \beta_5 B^2 + \beta_6 A^2 B + \beta_7 AB^2 + \beta_8 A^2 B^2,$$

where β_0 , the intercept, is the arithmetic average of all quantitative outcomes of nine runs, β_1 to β_8 are the coefficient computed from the observed experimental values of Y , and A and B are the coded levels of the independent variable(s). The terms AB and A^2 and B^2 are the interaction and polynomial terms, respectively. The main effects (A and B) postulate the

average result of changing one factor at a time from its low to high value. The interaction term (AB) shows how the response changes when two factors are changed accordingly. The polynomial terms (A^2 and B^2) symbolize nonlinearity.

Stability studies of the tablets

Stability of a formulation can be defined as the time from date on manufacture of the formulation until its chemical or biological activity is not less than a predetermined level of labeled potency and its physical characteristic have not changed appreciably or deleteriously. Formulation and the development of a pharmaceutical product are not complete without proper stability analysis, carried out on it to assess the physical and chemical stability and the safety. The purpose of stability testing is to provide evidence on how the quality of a drug substance or drug

product varies with time. Under the influence of a variety of environmental factors such as temperature, humidity and light, enabling recommended storage conditions, re-test periods and shelf lives. Generally, the observation of the rate at which the product degrades under normal room temperature requires a long time. To avoid the undesirable delay, the principles of accelerated stability studies are adopted. The International Conference on Harmonization (ICH) Guidelines titled "Stability testing of new drug substance and products" (Q1A) describes the stability test requirements for drug registration application in the European Union, Japan and United States of America.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION:

Preformulation:

Organoleptically properties of drug:

Table no 4: Organoleptic Properties.

S.No.	Properties	Result
1	Description	A white to off white powder
2	Colour	White
3	Odour	Odourless
4	Taste	Bitter

Discussion: From the given data in table 8.1 it was observed the organoleptic properties of test drug matches with the given standard data. This can be used as preliminary level

Melting Point:

Table 5: Melting Point of test drug

S.No	Observed melting point	Average melting point	Standard melting point
1	134°C-136°C		
2	133°C-134°C	136°C	136-145°C
3	136°C-145°C		

Discussion: As the result obtain in table no 8.2 it was observed that drug sample were perfectly match with given standard value which may in preliminary level

Partition coefficient:

Table 6: Partition coefficient

S.No	Observed log P	Standard log P
1	4.8	5.1

Discussion: As the experimental result reveal table no 8.4 the observed log p value of drug matches with the standard given value.

Solubility:

Table 7: Solubility studies of drugs in different solvent

S. No	Solvent	Solubility
1	Ethanol	soluble
2	Water	Insoluble
3	Acetone	Very soluble

Discussion: Form above the table no 8.4 the observed that the drug is soluble in ethanol, and acetone.

Identification of drug through FTIR:

Standard FTIR of Loratadine

Fig 3: FTIR Spectra of Loratadine (standard)

Table 8:: Functional group detection of Loratadine

Wave No.(cm-1)	Inference	Material
1702.28	C=O stretching	LORATADINE
713.22	C-Cl Stretching	
3037.27	C-H Stretching	
1591.37	C=N Stretching	
29.82.06	C-H Stretching	
1579.60	C-C Skeletal Stretching	
1355.68	C-N Stretching tertiary	

Discussion: Major functional groups present in Loratadine show characteristic peaks in IR Spectrum. Table 8.1 shows peaks observed at different wave numbers and the functional Group associated with these peaks. The major peaks are identical to functional group of Loratadine. Hence, the sample was confirmed as Loratadine.

Loss on drying:

The percentage loss on drying after 4 hours was found to be 0.4%. The sample passes test for loss on drying as per the limits specified in I.P. (N.M.T. 0.5%).

Table 9:: Percentage loss on drying for Loratadine

S.No	Percentage LOD	Avg. Percentage LOD
1	0.2	0.3± 0.1
2	0.3	
3	0.4	

Drug- Polymer Compatatibility Studies:

FTIR tests were performed for active ingredient as follows:

FTIR Scan of Loratadine:

Fig 4: FTIR of Loratadine (pure drug)

FTIR scan of Loratadine + Polymer

Table 10: Comparison tablet of peak of functional group of pure drug with drug and excipients.

S.NO	Wavelength(cm-1)		Standard Wavelength	Interpretation
	Drug	Drug+Excipients		
1	1700cm-1	1704cm-1	1800-1540cm-1	C=C Stretching
2	1547cm-1	1659cm-1	1667-1640cm-1	C=C Stretching
3	2900cm-1	2851cm-1	2273-200cm-1	C=N Stretching
4	1134cm-1	1395cm-1	1370-1220cm-1	C-H Bending
5	1235cm-1	948cm-1	1250-1020cm-1	C-N Stretching
6	1450cm-1	1350cm-1	1647-1505cm-1	C-N Vibrations Aliphatic

Discussion: Drug excipients compatibility study was performed by using FTIR by matching the main peak of drug with drug polymer mixture, there is no significant differences observed in between the peaks of drug- polymer mixture so it, may be concluded that there was no possible interaction between drug and polymer.

Analytical Methods.

Determination of λ -max. And Preparation of Calibration Curve of Loratadine

Loratadine by using 0.1 N HCl.

UV absorption spectrum of Loratadine in 0.1 N HCl shows λ -max at 247.5 nm. Absorbance obtained for various concentrations of Loratadine in 0.1 N HCl are given in table 8.4. The graph of absorbance vs. concentration for Loratadine was found to be linear in the concentration range of 10 μ g /ml. The drug obeys Beer- Lambert's law in the range of 10 μ g /ml.

Table 11: Data of Concentration and Absorbance

S.No.	Concentration(μ g/ml)	Absorbance at 247
1	5	0.153
2	10	0.314
3	15	0.452
4	20	0.625
5	25	0.789
6	30	0.985

Figure 5: UV Spectra of Loratadine in 0.1 N HCl

Evaluation of Loratadine Tablet Wafers.

Evaluation of Pre Compression Parameters Powder Blends of Loratadine Tablet Wafer

Table 12: Evaluation of Powder Blends of Loratadine

Formulation code	Bulk density(g/ml)	Tapped density(g/ml)	Angle of repose©	Carr, index (%)	Hauser's ratio
F1	0.45±0.0125	0.50±0.0231	31.78±1.8815	11.19±0.00	0.8880±0.00
F2	0.43±0.0165	0.49±0.0099	30.67±0.9514	11.45±0.00	0.8854±0.00
F3	0.45±0.0042	0.50±0.0063	34.53±1.7870	9.56±0.00	0.9043±0.00
F4	0.41±0.0105	0.47±0.0124	28.42±1.2725	12.26±0.00	0.8773±0.00
F5	0.45±0.0090	0.52±0.0213	33.78±1.4577	13.79±0.00	0.8620±0.00
F6	0.47±0.0120	0.54±0.0217	29.04±1.1461	12.69±0.00	0.8730±0.00
F7	0.46±0.0103	0.50±0.0107	33.65±0.5445	9.65±0.00	0.9034±0.00
F8	0.48±0.0134	0.56±0.0216	28.66±1.673	14.18±0.00	0.8581±0.00
F9	0.43±0.0171	0.48±0.0263	26.59±0.4705	10.31±0.00	0.8968±0.00

All values are expressed as mean± SE, n=3.

Angle of Repose:

The Angle of repose of various powder mixed blends, prepared with different Superdisintegrant was measured by funnel method. Angle of repose was found in the range $26.59 \pm 0.4705 - 34.530 \pm 1.7870$. The good flow ability of powder blend was also Evidence with angle of repose.

Bulk density:

The bulk density of various powder mixed blends prepared with different Superdisintegrant was

measured by graduated cylinder. The bulk density was found in the range $0.41 \pm 0.0105 - 0.48 \pm 0.0134$ g/ml

Tapped Density:

The Tapped density of various powder mixed blends prepared with different Superdisintegrant was measured by using measuring cylinder. The tapped density was found in the range $0.47 \pm 0.0124 - 0.56 \pm 0.0216$ g/ml. These values indicate good packing characteristics and the powder was not bulky

Compressibility Index:

The Compressibility index of various powder mixed blends, prepared with different Superdisintegrants, using bulk density and tapped density data, compressibility index was calculated. It was found in the range 9.56 ± 0.00 - 14.18 ± 0.00 %. This indicates good flow properties.

Hauser's Ratio:

The Hauser's ratio of various powder mixed blends, prepared with different Superdisintegrants, it is calculated by using bulk density and tapped density data. It was Found in the range of 0.8581 ± 0.00 - 0.9043 ± 0.00 , reveals good flow.

Evaluation of Loratadine tablet wafers:

Formulation code	Dimension		Hardness (kg/cm ²)	Friability (%)	Drug content(%w/w)	Weight variation
	Thickness(nm)	Diameter(nm)				
F1	2.90±0.10	7.86±0.20	3.26±0.05	0.8±0.05	98.50±0.11	204±1.18
F2	2.9±0.17	7.73±0.32	3.36±0.11	0.8±0.15	98.75±0.01	205.15±1.59
F3	2.76±0.25	7.8±0.24	3.26±0.15	0.9±0.1	98.25±0.15	206.15±1.63
F4	2.8±0.10	7.96±0.20	3.36±0.15	0.9±0.13	95.25±0.13	207.15±1.53
F5	2.7±0.17	7.76±0.32	3.33±0.25	0.8±0.07	98.50±0.06	207.10±1.61
F6	3.0±0.10	7.93±0.35	3.4±0.10	0.8±0.09	97.70±0.23	205.10±1.53
F7	2.8±0.11	7.76±0.30	3.4±0.10	0.8±0.06	97.75±0.14	201.55±1.65

Dimension (Thickness and Diameter):

Tablets were evaluated by using Venire caliper. Excessive variation in the tablet Thickness and diameter can result in problems with packaging as well as consumer Acceptance. There were no marked variations in the thickness and diameter of tablets within each formulation indicating uniform die fill throughout the compression process. The size (diameter) of the tablets of all formulations was found to be 7.73 ± 0.3214 - 7.96 ± 0.2081 mm and thickness of the tablets was found in the range of 2.70 ± 0.17 mm - 3.0 ± 0.10 mm.

Weight variation

Tablets were prepared using direct compression technique. Since the material was free flowing, tablets were obtained of uniform weight due to uniform die fill. Tablets were obtained in the range with acceptable weight variations as per Pharmacopoeia Specifications, less than 7.5.

Hardness

Tablets were evaluated by using Monsanto Hardness tester. Hardness of the tablets was in the range 3.0 ± 0.1 - 3.4 ± 0.1 kg/cm². Uniform hardness was obtained due to equal Compression force. The obtained hardness range showed good mechanical strength with an Ability to withstand physical and mechanical stress conditions.

Friability

Tablets were evaluated by using Roche Friabilator and friability of tablets was observed in acceptable range. 0.8 ± 0.090 - 0.9 ± 0.117 (less than 1%) This indicated a good Mechanical resistance of the prepared mouth dissolving tablet.

Drug content of Loratadine

Tablets were evaluated by using assay method. The drug content was obtained in the Acceptable limit. The drug content was found in the range 95.25 ± 0.13 - 98.75 ± 0.1 % w/w. (i.e. 99-101% w/w). The found range was within the specified limit as per India Pharmacopoeia 2007.

Disintegration time

Tablets were subjected for the *in-vitro* disintegrate time in the USP Disintegrate test apparatus. (Virgo scientific VTD-DV) The *in-vitro* disintegrate time for all nine Formulations varied from 12 ± 1.8973 to 30 ± 1.8973 seconds. The rapid disintegrate was seen in the formulations containing Crospovidone and Crosscarmellose sodium. This is due to rapid intake of the water from the medium, swelling and burst effect. It also noticed that the concentration of Crosscarmellose sodium followed by Crospovidone and Sodium starch glycolate increased, the time taken for the disintegrate was reduced. Disintegrate time was to be found very less for F9 formulation which contains highest Concentration and efficiency of Crospovidone.

Figure 6: Disintegration of tablet

Table 13: Disintegration time in seconds

Formulation	Disintegrate time (sec) (Mean±S.D.n=3)
F1	25±3.2863
F2	19±1.4142
F3	15±1.4142
F4	30±1.8973
F5	22±1.4142
F6	18±1.4142
F7	20±2.000
F8	15±1.4142
F9	12±1.89731

All values are expressed as mean± SE, n=3.

Table 14: *In-vitro* dissolution data of formulation F1

S.No.	Time (minutes)	Amount of drug released(mg)	%DE	MDT(minutes)	Cumulative% drug released
1	0	0.00	0.00	0.00	0±0.00
2	3	7.28	36.04	1.50	72.91±0.6266
3	6	7.64	55.24	1.69	76.42±0.7985
4	9	8.54	63.84	2.26	85.5±0.6221
5	12	8.81	69.60	2.57	88.14±0.2214

All the values are expressed as a mean ±SD, n=3

MDT=Mean dissolution time % DE=Percent dissolution efficiency

Figure 7: Cumulative% drug release profile formulation F1

Dissolution profile for formulation F2

Table 15: *In-vitro* dissolution data of formulation F2

S.No.	Time (minute)	Amount of drug released(mg)	% DE	MDT (minute)	Cumulative % drug release
1	0	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
2	3	7.63	37.96	1.50	76.34±0.98
3	6	8.06	58.12	1.68	80.88±0.94
4	9	8.78	66.72	2.11	87.34±0.854
5	12	9.23	72.32	2.51	91.79±1.097

All the values are expressed as a mean ± SD, n=3Fi

Figure 8: Cumulative % drug release profile F2

Dissolution Profile for Formulation F3

Table 16: *In-vitro* dissolution data of Formulation F3

S.No.	Time (minute)	Amount of drug released (mg)	%DE	MDT (minute)	Cumulative % drug Release
1	0	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
2	3	23.48	39.00	1.33	78.31±1.0102
3	6	25.14	41.21	1.42	83.81±0.9072
4	9	8.99	44.06	1.53	90.01±1.7596
5	12	9.35	45.61	1.58	93.54±0.9073

All the values are expressed as a mean ± SD., n = 3

Figure 9: Cumulative % drug release profile of formulation F3

Dissolution Profile for formulation F4

Table 17: *In-vitro* dissolution data of formulation F4

S.No.	Time (minute)	Amount of drug released (mg)	%DE	MDT (minute)	Cumulative % drug released
1	0	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00±0.00
2	3	7.01	35.07	1.50	70.20±1.9053
3	6	8.22	53.80	1.69	74.05±0.5212
4	9	8.9	61.71	2.07	80.16±1.0627
5	12	9.48	66.95	2.57	85.43±0.5692

All the values are expressed as a mean $\pm$ SD., n = 3

Figure 10: Cumulative % drug release profile of formulation F4

Dissolution Profile for Formulation F5

Table 18: in vitro dissolution data formulation F5

S.No.	Time (minute)	Amount of drug released(mg)	%DE	MDT (minute)	Cumulative % drug release
1	0	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
2	3	7.25	36.34	1.50	72.58 $\pm$ 0.4653
3	6	7.93	56.11	1.74	79.36 $\pm$ 1.5224
4	9	8.32	64.56	2.07	83.30 $\pm$ 2.9131
5	12	8.78	69.86	2.45	87.89 $\pm$ 1.3618

All the values are expressed as a Mean $\pm$ S.D.n=3

Figure 11: Cumulative % drug release profile of formulation F5

Dissolution profile for formulation F6

Table 19: in- vitro dissolution data of formulation F6

S.No.	Time (minute)	Amount of drug released(mg)	%DE	MDT (minute)	Cumulative % drug released
1	0	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
2	3	7.60	36.34	1.50	76.13±0.9595
3	6	8.09	58.30	1.60	80.97±1.3054
4	9	8.74	66.83	2.10	87.52±0.5105
5	12	9.09	72.38	2.44	90.96±0.6814

All the value are expressed as a mean $\pm$ SD, n=3

Figure 12: Cumulative % drug release Profile Formulation F6

CONCLUSION:

In conclusion, we reported here the formulation of LOR containing mucoadhesive wafers produced following design of experiment and optimized with the help of response surface methodology involving the factors as percentage of bucco adhesive polymer and hydrophilic matrix forming lactose monohydrate and responses taken as bio adhesive force, disintegration time, swelling percentage, and release (70%) of drug from the wafers. The wafer formulation coded as FNA 8 was found to be optimized with desirable bio adhesive strength, disintegration time, swelling property, and optimum drug release in the buccal environment. One of the advantages of oral wafer preparation was the ease in intake. The present wafer base preparation was found to be easily dissolving in saliva without producing insoluble materials. The constituents of the wafer base preparation had already been used in internal dosage additives and thus safe. These findings when taken to get her suggest that the present formulated mucoadhesive wafers containing Loratadine can be reproduced with high predictability and shall be

potentially useful to patients with dysphasia or a aphasia that require an immediate relief from the allergic conditions. The release of drug from the F-4 formulation was quick when compared to F-2 and F-3 formulation. It shows that the combined effect of crosscarmellose sodium and pharma burst B2 gives synergistic effect. Undoubtedly the availability of various technologies and the manifold advantages of MDT will surely enhance the patient compliance, low dosing, and rapid onset of action, increased bioavailability, low side effect, good stability and its popularity in near future.

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REFERENCE:

1. Amine P.D, Gupta S.S., Prabhu N.B., Wadhvani A.R., Fast disintegrating dosage form Of Ofloxacin and Metronidazole benzoate, Indian Drugs, Vol.42 (9), 2005, 614–617.
2. Amit Amanda., Kandarapu R., Garb S., An update on taste masking technologies for Oral Pharmaceuticals, Indian Journal of Pharmaceutics science, 2002, 10–17.
3. Anil Kumar, Benita, Prescription writing trends of anti histamines at the University Health Centre, Indian Journal of Pharmaceutical sciences, 2009,25–33.
4. Anne Waugh and Allison Grant., Ross and Wilson Anatomy and Physiology in Health and illness, 10th ed., Churchill living stone, London, 2006, 301-304.
5. Anonymous, CIMS, CPM Medical India Pvt. Ltd. Bangalore, 2011,470
6. Anonymous, <http://www.drugbank.ca/drugs/DB00186> accessed on 10 Dec. 2009.
7. Anonymous, <http://www.pharmainfo.net/reviews/new-generation-tablet-fastdissolving-tablet>, Accessed on 10 th December 2009.
8. Anonymous, <http://www.pharmpedia.com/Loratadine/spectroscopy/word#ixzz0quf>.
9. Anonymous, Indian Pharmacopoeia, Published by the Controller of Publication, Govt. Of India, Ministry of Health and Family Welfare, New Delhi, Vol.1, 2, 3, 2007, 1045.
10. Anonymous, The British Pharmacopoeia, London, Controller of her majesty's Stationary office, 2002.
11. Anonymous, the United States Pharmacopoeia, XXVII, NF XXII, The United States Pharmacopoeia convention Inc, Vol.2, 2009, 2175.
12. Anonymous, www.drugs.com, detail drug profile information.
13. Anonymous, www.ich.org/cache/compo.com, International Conference on Harmonization (ICH) guidelines Ansell H.C., Pelvic N. G. Introduction to Pharmaceutical Dosage form, 2nd ed. 1989, 265. 15) Ault on M.E. Eds. Pharmaceutics. The science of dosage form design, 3rd ed. Churchill Livingstone, New York, 2002, 441, 16-168.
14. Bandai Suresh, Retender Kumar Mitta pall, Ramsey Gannu., or dispersible tablets an Overview, Asian Journal of Pharmaceutics, Vol. 6 (35), 2008, 1-11. 17) Banker G.S., and Rhodes C.T. Eds. Modern Pharmaceutics, 3rd ed., Marcel Dekker, Inc. New York, 1996, 668-669.
15. Beckett A. H., Senlac J. B., Practical Pharmaceutical chemistry, CBS publishers, New Delhi, 4th ed., 2005, 278–280.
16. Brahmeshwar Mishear., Dali Shula., Subhashnis Chakra borty, Sanjay Singh., Mouth Dissolving Tablets, An Overview of Formulation Technology, Sci. Pharm., 2009, 77,309–326.
17. Chaudhari P. D., Chaudhari S. P., Lanker S. D., Patel Nakul., Formulation and in vitro Evaluation of taste masked or dispersible Levocetirizine dihydrochloride, Indian Journal of Pharmaceutical Education and Research, 2007, 41 (4).
18. Chaudhari P.D., Chaudhari S.P., Kosher S.R., Formulation and evaluation of Famotidine MDT, Indian Drugs, Vol. 42(10), 2005, 641–649.
19. Dekker series., Lachman Leon, Lieberman H.A., Pharmaceutical dosage forms, Tablets, vol.1, 87-98.
20. Devi V.K., Aisha A.N., Pail R.S., Reddy M.C.H., Raghavendra M.M.A.V. Or dispersible Fulconazole Tablets- Preparation and Evaluation, Indian Drugs, Vol.43 (7), 2006, 548–552
21. Dhanyakumar D. C., Dhananjay S. Ghodke., Rohit R Shah., Rahul Ghaste., Fast Dissolving Tablets, An Overview, Pharmainfo. Net, pharmaceutical reviews e Journal, 2010, Vol.8, 1-9.
22. Ganesh Kumar Gudas., Manassas B., Rajesh am V., Kiran Kumar S., and Prasanna Kumar J., Formulation and evaluation of fast dissolving tablets of Chlorpromazine hydrochloride, Journal of pharmaceutical sciences and technology, 2010, 2,99-102.
23. Gattani S. G., Kerkrade B. G., Patel A. B., Formulation and evaluation of Ondansetron Hydrochloride mouth dissolving Tablets, Indian Drugs, Vol. 46 (1), 2009, 44–60.
24. Gupta A., Mishear A. K., Gupta V., Basal P., Recent trends of fast dissolving Tablet an overview of formulation technology, International Journal of Pharmaceutical & Biological Archives, 2010, 1(1), 76-83.
25. Guarded R., Catwalk and Sham K., An and., Instrumental methods of chemical analysis, 2007, 2.747-2.750.
26. Halakatti P.K., Dandong P.M., Mastiholimath V.M., Patel M.B., Manvel F.V., Rapidly Disintegrating Domperidone Tablets, Indian Drugs, Vol. 43 (7), 2006, 594–597.
27. Hire math J.G., Shanty C.S., Srinath M.S., Pharmaceutical Approaches of Taste Masking in Oral Dosage Forms, Indian Drugs, Vol. 4 (5), 2004, 253–257

28. Villanovan Ponnilaravasan., Cheered Sunil .Nerada Kumar., Simultaneous estimation of Ambroxol hydrochloride and Loratadine in tablet dosage form by using UV spectrophotometric method, International journal of pharmacy and bioscience,2011, 2, 338-344.
29. Jens T. Christensen., C. T. Rhodes., Text Book of Drug Stability, Principal and practices,3rd edn.,2001.
30. John H Block., John M., Beale Jr., Wilson and Griswold's., Text book of organic medical and P'ceutical chemistry, 2nd end. Lippincott Williams and Wilkins, 2004,702.
31. Kaushik D., Diuretic H., Sinai T.R., Formulation and evaluation of olanzapine mouth Dissolving tablets by effervescent formulation approach, Indian Drugs, Vol. 4(7),2004, 410-412.
32. Kenny R.V., Charisma Desouza and Lourenco C.F., Formulation and evaluation of Rizatriptan Benzoate mouth disintegrating tablets, Indian J.Pharm, Sci., 2010, 72(1),79-85.
33. Kieran Crowley., R. Bohnacker., or dispersible Tablets at a glance, A Literature From pharmpedia, 79-94.43) Mishear D.N., Bindle M., Singh S.K., Kumar S.G.V., Rapidly disintegrating oral tablets Of Valdecocixib.Indian Drugs, Vol. 42 (10), 2005, 685-687.
34. Mishear D.N., Vijay a K.S.G., Rapidly disintegrating oral tablets of Meloxicam, India Drugs, Vol. 43(2), 2006, 117-121. 45) Muffed A.C., Skelton M.D.,Widdop B., Clarke's analysis of drugs & poisons, 3rd Edition, Pharmaceutical press, 2004. Vol.2, 935.46)Mohan A., Gosh S. K., Fast dissolving tablets, Past, present and future, Indian drug,2010, 47(6), 5-11.
35. Mukesh G., Patel M., Avanti A., Agrawal R., Dave R., Beria N., Formulation design And optimization of mouth dissolve tablets of Nimusulide using vacuum drying Technique, AAPS Parma Sci. Tech, 2006, Vol. 5 (3), 2004, 36-45.
36. Panigrahi D., Bagels S., Mishear B., Mouth dissolving tablets an overview of Preparation techniques, evaluation and patented technologies, Journal of Pharmaceutical Research, Vol. 4 (7), 2005, 33-38.
37. Raymond C., Rowe., Paul J., Whiskey and Sian C., Owen., Hand book of Pharmaceutical Excipients,4th end., Pharmaceutical press, London,2003.
38. Reddy L.H., Ghost B, Rajneesh, Fast dissolving drug delivery systems a review of the Literature, Indian J. pharm. Sci., Vol. 64 (4), 2002, 33-36.
39. Roberta M., Silverstein, Francis X., Spectrometric identification of organic compounds, 6th edn, 2003, 71-144.
40. Rosie McLaughlin., Susan Ban bury, Kieran Crowley., Orally disintegrating tablets, The Effect of Recent FDA Guidance on ODT Technologies and Applications, Pharmaceutical Technology, U.S.A.2009, 97-107.
41. Kuchekar B.S., Bashan A.C., Malayan H.S., mouth dissolving tablets of Salbutamol Sulphate A Novel drug delivery system, Indian Drugs, Vol. 41 (10)2004, 592-598.
42. Lachman L., Lieberman H.A., and Kanig J.L., The theory and practice of Industrial Pharmacy,3rd edition, Varghese Publishing House, Mumbai,1991,67-71,183-184.
43. Lela J.K., Mamania H., Fast dissolving Rofecoxib tablets, Indian J. pharm. sci. Vol.4, 2004, 350-352.
44. Mallikarjunasettee C., Prasad D.V.K., Gupta R.M., Development of fast dispersible Aceclofenac tablets, Indian Journal of Pharmaceutical sciences, 2008, 180-185.53) Roop K. Khar., Harmik Sochi and Yemen Sultana, Taste Masking Technologies in Oral Pharmaceuticals, Recent Developments and Approaches, Drug Development and Industrial Pharmacy, 2001, 30, 429-448.
45. Sajal Kumar Jha., Divakar goli, Formulation and evaluation of melt-in-mouth tablets Of Haloperidol, Asian Journal of Pharmaceutics, 2008, Vol (3), 276-298.
46. Sager H., Drug-Delivery Products and Xydis Fast-Dissolving Dosage Form, J.Pharm. Pharmacology, 1998, 375-382.
47. Shenoy V., Pandey S., Agrawal S., optimizing fast dissolving dosage form of Diclofenac sodium by rapidly disintegrating agent, Indian Journal of Pharmaceutics Science,2003,197-200.
48. Shirwaikar A. A., Ravi Kumar. Shirwaikar Annie., Mahalaxmi R., Formulation and Evaluation of mouth dissolving tablet of Metformin HCl, Int. Journal PharmacyExcept,2006, 86-92.
49. Shirwaikar A., Aithal K., Harish N.M., Rathnanand M., Dutta M., Once daily fast Dissolving tablets of Granisetron Hydrochloride formulation and in vitro evaluation, Indian drugs, Vol.43 (7), 2006, 576-582.
50. Shirwaikar A.A., Ramsey A., Fast Disintegrating Tablets of Atenolol by Dry Granulation method, Indian J. Pharm. Sci.Vol. 66(4), 2004, Shish. Bhatt A., Fast disintegrating tablet of Diazepam, Indian Drugs, Vol. 43(8)2006, 643-648.